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SOME FEATURES IN THE MODEL OF INTERACTION OF THE ORGANISM WITH OTHER OBJECTS

Abstract.

The main part of this work is formed on hypothesis, which, accordingly, require partial proof. In general, the author attempts to form a model of an artificial central nervous system; including, in this work, partially and briefly, the operating principle of the system is described. The work describes information regarding the results of interaction between organisms that have a mutual connection, including, with the help of the phenomenon of telepathy, which leads to a change in conditions of the health of the organism and of its homeostasis in society. Crime is one of the possible ways to harm the health of the organism. Thus, the work, briefly, describes some of the possible ways of influencing the organism, in order to reduce the quality of its health condition.

Keywords: information transfer, telepathy, stress, health, central nervous system, artificial central nervous system, artificial intelligence, crime.

Introduction.

Today, artificial intelligence technologies are actively developing [1, 2]. An equally important part of this is the improvement of methods that describe the design and operation of robots, including humanoid robots [3].

The author, based on known information from the field of medical sciences, as well as his own hypotheses, is attempting to form a model of an artificial central nervous system (NS, CNS, ACNS) – as, in turn, partially, improving the methods and means of the discipline of artificial intelligence [4-7].

Definition of the problem.

One of the problems that arose in the process of forming the ACNS model is that there is a lack of some important information regarding the interaction between the organism and other objects (including, other organisms), which, without defining this and including it in the general knowledge base, ultimately leads to less realistic behaviour of the system [5].

Basically, the essence of the problem indicates a lack of knowledge regarding the process of exchanging information through the phenomenon of telepathy, which plays an important role in the overall work of society.

The purpose of this study is to determine the features of interaction between one living organism and others, as well as the external environment, which should be taken into account when forming the ACNS model.

Results.

It should be noted that all the features that will be listed below are interconnected with each other and could be defined in one point, but in order to express the result in several points, due to the possible application of individual features to these, the result is presented in several points – features.

In the process of processing the problem, it became clear that the ACNS, that is being formed, cannot be a separate – independent, system from other objects.

Therefore, it would be wrong, for example, in the process of developing this to use only one copy of such a system – there must be more than one such system, since they have a connection that ensures the maintenance of homeostasis of these in society and, accordingly, the health condition of these, with each other through the phenomenon of telepathy.

Therefore, today, it has become possible to highlight the following features. This was obtained using assumptions, which, of course, requires evidence – the results of separate experiments.

General homeostasis in society.

As was stated above in the text, the system – the organism, cannot be or exist alone – be isolated from others, since such a "path", after some time, leads to the destruction of the health of this.

Therefore, it can be assumed that the systems that interact in society, interact according to the laws of energy propagation.

Thus, the system – the organism, the amount of energy of which is less, is able to restore a certain amount when interacting with a separate group of systems. According to information from the field of medicine, this is described as an increase in the release of separate substances – primarily, oxytocin, dopamine and gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA), and, accordingly, an improvement in the health condition of the organism, during communication, the result of which is satisfactory for this.

Actually, the exchange of energy in this way can be carried out without traditional methods, information about which a person has, in a certain, sufficient amount, of information transfer. Accordingly, the method of communication can be different – through the phenomenon of telepathy, where information can be transmitted, to a greater extent, and without third-party skills, unconsciously.

The conclusion of this may be that every interaction – including, one that one of the parties may not know about, since it did not take place as a connection between organisms using at least one of the main 5

senses, between organisms must be accompanied by the transfer of information through the phenomenon of telepathy (6th sense).

Changes in homeostasis as a result of exposure to criminal methods.

Any refusal in something to the organism or deprivation of something can be the cause of the development of mental disorders – such as, for example, schizophrenia, which is accompanied by hallucinations. If the system is not previously prepared for such conditions, then the work of the hippocampus is disrupted and, depending on the degree of damage that has been inflicted, a state similar to "hopelessness" may arise, when this brain part is not able to predict further actions. As a result, dissociative identity disorder develops.

One of the methods, that relates to the type of crime, describes external influence, through the phenomenon of telepathy, a negative type, on the health of the "victim's" organism, which, as a result, disrupts the quality of the work of substances – primarily, serotonin, dopamine and GABA – if the organism is not prepared for such conditions earlier. In this case, there is also a disruption of the hippocampus. Therefore, as a result of the impact of a "predator" (or a group of "predators") that have an excess of released substances, the "victim's" system becomes deprived of calm. Probably, at such a moment, the system releases adrenaline in large quantities, which disrupts the general activity of the system; at the same time, activating the effect of the "instinct of self-preservation", in which the system, which is under pressure, releases a greater number of substances in moments of stress. Such an effect is quite possible under the condition of impaired quality of metabolism and / or plasticity of the nervous system.

Another method, under the same conditions, describes keeping the "victim" in a state of impaired health condition, for a long time, for the purpose of "profit" – usually, for the purpose of stealing property, while the "victim" is in an unhealthy state – the work of the hippocampus is impaired and schizophrenia is in effect; after committing a theft, the "predator" can wait for a period of time, carrying out the same actions, until the moment when the body system of the "victim" can act against it – for example, contact the service in order to protect their rights. Ultimately, the "victim" is deprived of their property and the memory, in relation to this, becomes distorted. However, all this occurs taking into account the disease – a mental disorder.

Also, if, in part, the requirements for the principle of operation of storing information in the central nervous system are the work of inhibition of excitation with the help of substances – such as GABA, as well as the work of dopamine, the required quality value, then the effect of "imposed, separate action", which can cause harm to the "victim", under certain conditions, can be performed by means of a method that can be attributed, of course, to criminal methods, which describes the training of the nervous system of an organism, which is subjected, in a sense, to sadistic actions, with the subsequent preservation in the memory of the "victim" of actions that, in the future, can be caused by "predators" in order to reduce the quality of life of the "victim";

while the course of action of which, possibly, is as follows: the central nervous system of the "victim" is subject to influence, including, with the help of the phenomenon of telepathy, in order to disrupt the quality of metabolism – close, to impotence of the CNS and peripheral NS (PNS), parts of the brain (B); then, probably, by actions that are similar to the previous ones, the "predator" introduces the required information – probably, usually, aggression, which is not subject to its own control; then, when restoring, to a certain level, the quality of the work of the metabolism of substances and B parts, this information is reproduced.

The results of the methods can be achieved if the "victim" has a small number of contacts – accordingly, low energy.

Homeostasis in "parasitism" or "vampirism" effects.

The homeostasis of the organism can change, as well as the energy of the "victim's" organism, with trust in a separate object.

With such an effect as "parasitism" there should be a violation of the quality of work of most substances and B parts. This should probably be connected with the effect of "drug addiction", too.

One of the ways behind such an effect, which can also be considered as a criminal type method, is one in which the system of the "victim", which has undergone partial impotence – disruption of the work of dopamine, B, can be "led" with the help of information that is transmitted through hallucinations (hypnosis), through the work of the unconscious state.

Methods of protecting the organism's health.

Methods of protecting the health of the organism, which can receive violations due to the influence of the actions of offenders for the methods that are given, above, in the text, the following can be distinguished.

Since the quality of the work of the metabolism of the system, probably, has a low value, which can also be defined as impotence (depression) of the body – the CNS and the PNS, respectively, to restore and/or maintain the state of health, it is necessary to use means, the actions of which are aimed at replenishing the insufficient amount of substances in the organism.

However, first of all, the method that is able to maintain homeostasis of the organism is stimulation of individual actions that are aimed at maintaining the required mode of operation of the system.

This has already been indicated in the work [7]. Here, the information is presented, somewhat, in greater quantity.

In addition, actions that are aimed at the emergence of connections between organisms in society can lead to the replenishment of energy that was probably lost – the work that is disrupted, substances.

Conclusion.

According to the information that was given as hypotheses, the following conclusion can be made – the system cannot exist in a single copy, since, after a certain period of time, this leads to the loss of control over the actions of one's own consciousness – as the development of mental disorders – such as, for example, schizophrenia, therefore, such systems must exist in two copies, at least.

This means that the model of the ACNS must be formed with the inclusion of this knowledge.

However, how will this be accomplished?

The system, according to the model, is able to interact with the outside world using 6 senses, where 6 is the phenomenon of telepathy. Together, two or more systems are able to exchange information using these.

Changes in the quality of the metabolism of each organism contribute to a change in homeostasis in society. So, if the health of one of the organisms (a separate copy – an object, with an ACNS), which had a large number of substances, somewhat worsened, then another could replace it according to the principle of leadership in the group.

Development is facilitated by the correct operation of the system, which includes separate B parts and separate substances in the correct proportions – one of the main substances of development is probably dopamine (in large quantities). A decrease in the quality of cognitive abilities is facilitated by a disruption in the work of these parts and substances.

Darwin's theory can be described in this way, taking into account that deoxyribonucleic acid was subject to mutations, which improved the cognitive abilities of future generations of organisms. It, probably, made sense in the general group of ancient primates (in the future, "homo sapiens"), to use some individual primates for certain purposes with the aim of development and survival of the group, in general.

Information sources

1. Cheng-Tek Tai M. The Impact of Artificial Intelligence on Human Society and Bioethics / M. Cheng-Tek Tai // Tzu Chi Medical Journal. – 2020. – Vol. 32. – Is. 4. – 339-343 pp. DOI: 10.4103/tcmj.tcmj_71_20

2. Rawas S. AI: The Future of Humanity / S. Rawas // Discover Artificial Intelligence. – 2024. – Vol. 4. – 25. DOI: 10.1007/s44163-024-00118-3

3. Advancements in Humanoid Robots: A Comprehensive Review and Future Prospects / Y. Tong, H. Liu and Z. Zhang // IEEE/CAA Journal of Automatica Sinica. – 2024. – Vol. 11. – Is. 2. – 301-328 pp. DOI: 10.1109/JAS.2023.124140

4. Tomashuk A. Information for Forming a Model of Artificial Intelligence, Which Describes Work of the Human Central Nervous System / A. Tomashuk // Colloquium-journal. – 2022. – Vol. 17. – Is. 140. – 30-45 pp. DOI: 10.24412/2520-6990-2022-17140-30-45

5. Tomashuk A. Some Information about a Structure of Parts of the Central Nervous System / A. Tomashuk // Colloquium-journal. – 2023. – Vol. 27. – Is. 186. – 44-72 pp. DOI: 10.24412/2520-6990-2023-27186-44-72

6. Tomashuk A. Hypothesis Regarding a Principle of Work of the Phenomenon of Telepathy / A. Tomashuk // Colloquium-journal. – 2024. – Vol. 29. – Is. 222. – 46-53 pp. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13969436

7. Tomashuk A. Theoretical Information Regarding Methods and Means of Protection and Restoration of Health of the Organism Which is Subject to Communication with the Help of the Phenomenon of Telepathy / A. Tomashuk // Colloquium-journal. – 2024. – Vol. 31. – Is. 224. – 50-53 pp. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14098612